

EU Wayfinder

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

EU funding—especially Horizon Europe—can be complex, with dense terminology and layered governance. This cheatsheet offers shortcuts to help you navigate it more easily.

Benefits

Quick access to essential info saves time and reduces frustration, especially for smaller or practice-based partners in MAA projects. Ideal for both newcomers and those needing a refresher.

Practical recommendations

Just introduced to Horizon Europe—now what?

Horizon's complexity is well known. For smaller organisations, especially practitioner partners in MAA projects, the administrative burden can be a serious barrier. It's important to build early understanding of both the funding structure and the expectations involved.

- General context: Start with the [Horizon Europe Programme Guide](#) for an overview of the programme's logic, rules, and structure.
- Finding relevant calls:

Navigate to the [EU Funding & Tenders Portal](#) and explore the Clusters under Pillar II to browse current and upcoming calls. Curious about what has been done in the past? Check out the [CORDIS Database](#).

Lost in the jargon?

You're not alone. Even experienced participants wrestle with Horizon terminology. Thankfully, several useful glossaries exist:

- [European Commission Glossary](#).
- [Liaison Glossary](#).
- [BRIDGE2HEU Glossary](#).

Prefer learning through networking and events?

Engaging directly with people can speed up understanding and offer valuable insider tips.

- Reach out to your National Contact Point (NCP) for tailored guidance and support.
- Attend [Horizon Info Days](#) for a thematic overview of open calls.
- Check the [EU Commission Calendar](#) to find relevant workshops, webinars, and matchmaking events in your field.

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Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Active participation of, and focus on end-users.

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[Horizon Europe Programme Guide](#)

[EU Funding & Tenders Portal](#)

[CORDIS Database](#)

[European Commission Glossary](#)

[Horizon Info Days](#)

[EU Commission Calendar](#)

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